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A New Approach for Detecting Active Insect Infestation in Museum Objects Using Non-dispersive Infrared Spectroscopy

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Abstract

This study presents a novel approach for detecting active insect infestation in museum objects using non-dispersive infrared spectroscopy (NDIR). The method rapidly measures CO₂ emissions from living insects, enabling faster detection than traditional techniques. Laboratory and field tests with ancient Egyptian artefacts demonstrate the system's accuracy, sensitivity, and potential for post-treatment evaluation.

Keywords: Insect infestation; respired CO₂; NDIR; Telaire; artefact; GEM

1. Introduction

For seven years, the Conservation Centre in the Grand Egyptian Museum (GEM) has been receiving artefacts from different museums and archaeological sites and struggling to combat the insect infestations encountered in them. The most challenging and critical stage has long been the detection of active infestation within artefacts. In response to the increasing frequency of object transportation prior to the opening of the GEM, a correspondingly faster insect detection technique was deemed necessary. Detection of insect infestation in museum objects poses a serious challenge, usually met by using visual assessment, insect trapping, or acoustic detection. All can be impractical as they depend on insect movement, while living insects constitute but one part of the life cycle: the results obtained may thus be misleading. Impracticability may also arise from time constraints, lack of trained personnel or potential effects on museum objects (Koestler, Sardjono, and Koestler 2000). One promising technique based on detecting CO₂ respiration by active insects using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was developed by Koestler et al. at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, U.S.A. Although the system is indeed reliable and quick, it is still complicated and very costly, therefore museums in general have limited access to it.

2. Theory and Principle of NDIR CO₂ Sensing

CO₂ is one of the most common byproducts of living organisms. Insects may produce CO₂ at rates of about 1 μL/insect/min (1 ppm/min) (Street and Bruce 1976). The analysis of CO₂ gas has a long history involving several methods, including non-dispersive infrared spectroscopy (NDIR), an optical method of detecting and quantifying gases by their specific absorbed IR wavelengths (Stuart 2004; Korre et al. 2012; Gibson and MacGregor 2013). Gaseous CO₂ has a characteristic IR absorption at a wavelength of 4.26 μm, not found for

other common gases or in water vapour. The gas concentration is calculated by simply measuring how much IR light is absorbed at that wavelength. This technology is widely used for the real-time measurement of CO₂ in situ (Korre et al. 2012).

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 CO₂ Monitor Configuration

The CO₂ sensor utilised in this paper (Figure 1) is a hand-held Telaire 7001 monitor that measures CO₂ in the range 0 to 10,000 ppm with a sensitivity of ± 1 ppm. It comprises four elements; IR source, gas chamber, detector and electronics. The IR source is an incandescent mid-IR lamp with broadband emission. A key characteristic of this instrument is its gas sampling chamber with a waveguide structure designed using optical ray tracing (Nelson 2009); inwardly facing specularly reflective surface (Wong 1991) which defines the light path causing a reduction in light transmission at the sensing wavelength, and optimised beam bath length for the anticipated gas concentration range. Another key characteristic is the dual beam detector with two detectors, each with a different narrow bandpass filter to remove extraneous wavelengths (Wong 1994). The Telaire monitor is characterised by automatic background calibration (ABCLogic), which utilises the naturally fairly stable CO₂ air content to correct automatically for any long-term sensor drift. The monitor displays the measurements on a screen and can log measurements when connected to a HOBO U12 datalogger.

3.2 Target Insects

Respired CO₂ was measured for the cigarette beetle *Lasioderma serricorne* at different developmental stages, using three adults, two larvae and one pupa (Figure 2). These were kept in a plastic box with a muslin cover to allow gas exchange with the surrounding microenvironment.

Figure 1: The NDIR CO₂ detection system applied to six cigarette beetles. Photo: Manar Elkhial

Figure 2: The NDIR CO₂ detection system with a CO₂ monitor connected to a logger, heat-sealed with four suspected ancient Egyptian objects in ESCAL. Photo: Manar Elkhial

3.3 Measurement Procedure

The monitor is calibrated to ambient CO₂ level (400 ppm), connected to the logger, and quarantined with live insects in heat-sealed, gas-impermeable Escal plastic film (Mitsubishi Gas Company Inc., U.S.A.) to prohibit the mixture of respired gases with outside air. Another monitor is calibrated to the ambient CO₂ level and placed outside the bag. Four ancient Egyptian wooden artefacts previously attacked by insects

were selected for testing the efficiency of the new approach. The objects exhibited different signs of infestation, including live egg sacs. They were quarantined with the same system to detect active infestation. After insect eradication treatment was carried out, the objects were re-quarantined to evaluate the treatment. The change in CO₂ over time was recorded throughout.

4. Results

Figure 3 shows dramatic accumulation of CO₂ as a result of the respiration of the cigarette beetles. Although only six insects were visibly present, the accumulation of CO₂ in the first hour (900 ppm) compared to the level outside the bag (420) indicates the presence of nonvisible and/or dormant stages. This indicates the high sensitivity and fast response of this method, which is capable of revealing dormant or immobile infestations.

As for detecting active infestations in the four objects, Figure 4 shows the accumulation of CO₂ in the inspection bag compared to outside. The infestation was detectable within less than 60 minutes. Results obtained from after-treatment quarantine showed no accumulation of CO₂. Both experimental and applied approaches demonstrated that the system is able to determine activity from an infestation in a few hours, reliably (Figures 3 and 4).

5. Discussion

The method demonstrates high sensitivity and rapid detection capability. It offers a cost-effective, non-invasive alternative to existing techniques, with potential applications in routine museum pest management and conservation treatment assessment.

Figure 3: CO₂ measurements for cigarette beetles using the new system, compared to ambient level.

Figure 4: CO2 measurements using the new system for four ancient Egyptian objects during inspection and after-treatment quarantine compared to ambient level.

6. Conclusion

The new system was used to demonstrate rapid detection of insect infestation in archaeological objects. The results proved that the system is able to detect and record a change in CO₂ within a working day, providing reliable results in a few hours. It is also useful in evaluating the effectiveness of insect eradication treatments. The system has performance advantages in terms of cost efficiency, long-term stability, accuracy, high selectivity and sensitivity, and low power consumption, due to the NDIR technology configuration.

References

- Gibson, D., and C. MacGregor. 2013. "A Novel Solid State Non-dispersive Infrared CO₂ Gas Sensor Compatible with Wireless and Portable Deployment." *Sensor* 13: 7079–7103.
- Koestler, R. J., S. Sardjono, and D. L. Koestler. 2000. "Detection of Insect Infestation in Museum Objects by Carbon Dioxide Measurement Using FTIR." *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation* 46: 285–292.
- Korre, A., S. Durucan, C. E. Imrie, F. May, M. Krueger, K. Spickenbom, S. Schlömer, et al. 2012. *Quantification Techniques for CO₂ Leakage: IEA GHG R&D Programme*. UK: IEA Environmental Projects Ltd. (IEAGHG), 7.
- Nelson, A. 2009. "GE-Telaire NDIR System." In *Functional Thin Films and Nanostructures for Sensors: Synthesis, Physics and Applications*, edited by A. Zribi and J. Fortin, 98–102. New York (NY): Springer Science & Business Media.
- Street, M. W., and W. A. Bruce. 1976. "Hidden-Insect Detection by Infrared Carbon Dioxide Gas Analysis: Principles of System Design." *Agricultural Research Service (U.S. Department of Agriculture) ARS-S-85*: 1–10.
- Stuart, B. H. 2004. *Infrared Spectroscopy: Fundamentals and Applications: Analytical Techniques in the Sciences*. Hoboken: Wiley.
- Wong, J. Y. 1991. Gas sample chamber. United States of America Patent 5,163,332, November 17. Wong, J. Y. 1994. NDIR gas sensor. United States of America Patent 5,444,249, August 2.